

BEHAVIOR OF ADHESIVELY BONDED FRP BEAM-TO-COLUMN CONNECTIONS

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ABSTRACT

The focus of this work was to study the behavior of adhesive joints of fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) pultruded beam-to-column connections. I-section beams constructed from glass/epoxy fibrous composite, which were connected together only by an epoxy-type adhesive, were investigated. Three-dimensional finite element models were employed to analyze the static behavior of the beam-to-column pultruded sections to failure. In addition, an experimental study was performed on two different specimens to validate the finite element results. Comparisons between the numerical and experimental results suggests that the performance of adhesive joints can accurately be predicted by finite-element modeling.

INTRODUCTION

During the past few decades, composite materials have increasingly been used for structural, electrical, electronics and mechanical applications because of their superior properties. While composites have been extensively used in the aerospace and defense industries, they have had only limited use in civil infrastructures. This is mainly due to the high cost of these materials. It is anticipated that as the usage volume of the material increases, the price will lower and the more competitive advanced composites will become compared to conventional construction materials.

The use of high-strength, light-weight composites can be very useful especially in the areas of strengthening and rehabilitation of civil structures. A key aspect of any building material is how the building elements are joined together. Some of the conventional joining methods like welding and brazing may not be suitable for joining most composites. In non-civil engineering applications adhesives are extensively used.

Adhesives have been used for centuries. Over the past decades researchers have studied the characteristics of adhesion and improve their quality. A number of different adhesives are available commercially (e.g., Epoxy, Phenolic, Nitrile and Vinyl adhesives [1]). Adhesives offer several advantages for connecting FRP structural elements. These advantages are: 1) adhesive joints have

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uniform stress distribution; 2) larger stress bearing areas; 3) resistance to fatigue and impact; 4) adhesives have the capability to join dissimilar materials; 5) high strength-to-weight ratio; and, 6) act as sealants and provide protection against electrochemical corrosion.

Sawa *et al* [2] investigated the stress distribution and displacements at the interface between an adhesive and adherend for a T-type butt adhesive joint subjected to an external bending moment. They concluded that the ratio $E1/E2$, Young's modulus of the adherend to that of the adhesive, had a great effect on the normal and shear stresses at the interface between the adhesive and the adherend. The decrease in the thickness of the adhesive layer also increases the stress concentration at the end of the interface. According to Yamaguchi *et al* [3], reinforcement of a T-type adhesive butt joint resulted in a magnification of the strength. They proposed equations to calculate the stresses and the stress magnification factor. Chen *et al* [4] studied the fatigue behavior of adhesive bonded plastic-to-plastic joints and metal-to-plastic joints under dynamic and static loading. They found that the fatigue life of the joints was independent of the frequencies but was dependent on the mean stress level. Mosallam and Bank [5] investigated the behavior of a pultruded FRP portal frame subjected to static loads. Both analytical and experimental studies were performed. Flexibility of the beam-to-column bolted joint was found to control the overall behavior of the structure. The stiffness and the strength of the web-flange intersection were found to influence the beam-to-column stiffness of the frame. Abd-El-Naby and Hollaway [6,7] have examined the behavior of single and double-bolt joints for pultruded glass/polyester material. Single-bolt joints depend on the size of the clamping area and the material used for clamping influences the behavior of the joint greatly. It was also shown that for pultruded lay-ups, the low shear strength of the material does not allow bearing failure to occur. Double-bolted joints employing two bolts in series were also investigated. The experimental results demonstrated that using double-bolt joints increases the efficiency of the joints in FRP pultruded elements. For joints which fail in shear through the bolts, it was suggested that bolts be arranged in parallel may prove to be more efficient because this increases the resisting area failure. Martin [8] demonstrated that adhesive bonding technique can be used to strengthen existing fatigue prone steel structures. It was also shown that bonded transverse intermediate web stiffeners perform better than welded transverse intermediate web stiffeners. Davies *et al* [9], have compared two approaches to join thermoplastic composites. One approach was adhesive bonding with conventional epoxy adhesive and the second was fusion bonding by local melting in the area of the joint. They concluded that carbon-fiber composites can be assembled and repaired by both the methods efficiently. Shi and Cheng [10] considered the stress distribution in adhesive bonded cylindrical lap joints. Numerical models have been suggested by Shi and Cheng to illustrate the effect of stress distribution and intensities on the strength of the joint. Previous studies done have produced a basic understanding of the behavior of simple adhesive joints, and have developed suggestions for fabricating lap and T-shaped joints.

Though research has been done, very little is known about the application of adhesive joints to beam-column-connections. The objective of this study was to investigate the behavior adhesive joints in pultruded FRP sections for civil structures applications.

MATERIAL SELECTION

Material selection includes the testing of various kinds of adhesives and selecting the most suitable adhesive for the purpose of fabricating the beam-to-column adhesive joint. Description of the properties of the glass fiber reinforced epoxy composite used in the experiments is also included.

Five different types of adhesives were tested, two of these adhesives were eliminated in the initial stages since they were inadequate in many respects: strength, insufficient working time, and high flowability. Three adhesives were tested and Fusor 320/322, an adhesive manufactured by Lord's Corporation was selected for fabricating the beam-to-column adhesive connection. This adhesive had the highest strength and was easy to work with during fabrication.

The Fusor 320/322 adhesive selected is an epoxy adhesive. It is a two part epoxy-based adhesive designed to bond epoxy matrix FRP to another similar FRP or metal. The two parts, resin and hardener, are commercially available. Before application, the two parts should be thoroughly mixed in 1:1 ratio by weight for best results, until a consistent gray color paste is obtained. According to the manufacturer's data, the pot life of the mixed adhesive is 15 minutes at 25°C [11]. Pot life indicates the time period available to work with the adhesive before it starts to set.

The FRP composite components that were used for fabricating the joint specimens were provided by the Creative Pultrusions, Inc. The FRP materials are a combination of glass fibers and an epoxy matrix. Pultrusion methods were employed to manufacture these components. The engineering constants of FRP composite components are tabulated in Table 1. These properties were provided by the manufacturer [12]. The beam is light gray in color and is made of Isopolyester resin. The connections were angles sections. These are olive green and made of Isophthalic polyester, while the column is beige in color and is made of Vinylester. All the components contain 40-45% glass fiber. The properties of the beam and the angles do not differ from each other but the properties of the column vary slightly. In the analysis, it was assumed that all the components had the same properties as the beam and angles.

FINITE ELEMENT MODELING

In this work, a finite element method was used to study the behavior of the adhesively bonded FRP beam-to-column connections. It should be mentioned that after analyzing the first model by the finite element method, a specimen was built and tested. The second specimen was built based on the observation of the numerical and the test results of the first one. In the second model (and specimen) a supporting plate were added to the connection area to strengthen the joints. NISA II finite element software was used for all computations [13].

The primary focus was on the adhesive joints. Several assumptions were made for the modeling: 1) the adhesive was assumed to be a linear elastic material; 2) effective Young's and shear moduli were considered for defining the material properties of the FRP sections and angles; 3) biaxial bending was not considered in the model; 4) glass/epoxy beams were considered to behave similarly in tension and compression; 5) thermal and environmental condition effects were neglected. The tests were done in the Laboratory at room temperature. The geometrical dimensions and boundary conditions of the FRP beam, column and angles are given in Table 2.

The three-dimensional solid element was found to be inadequate for static analysis of the beam-to-column adhesive joint because this element is not accurate for high aspect ratios. The ratio of lengths of any two sides is called the aspect ratio. The elements in the area of the adhesive layers are subjected to very high aspect ratios and due to this elements in the other components also had high aspect ratios. Hence, a 3-D hybrid element was incorporated throughout the model. This element is basically a solid brick element but has the capability to handle aspect ratios as high as 10^3 . The element has three degrees of freedom (UX, UY, UZ) at each node and the stresses are characterized by six components (SXX, SYY, SZZ, SXY, SYZ, SXZ). The element incorporated was a eight-node hexadron. Effective moduli and Poisson's ratio were used to define the material properties of all the components and the adhesive layers.

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

Two beam-to-column adhesive joint specimens were prepared and tested in this investigation. The test specimens were gripped between clamping plates as shown in Figure 1a and the side view of the joint region are illustrated in Figures 1b. The clamps were fastened to the wall with 1-1/4" Dywidag bars. A thick steel plate was used as a washer for the nuts. The clear span of the column between the supports was 44.0". AISC standards for steel members were used to estimate the capacity of the web in web crippling and buckling [14]. The validity of the AISC formulas for steel beams to FRP beams was unknown. Hence, extra reinforcement was provided to the column in the area of the clamps on the web. Steel plates were glued to the web to prevent local stress effects and increase the load bearing capacity of the web in these regions. Load was applied in a 4" x 4" region, at the end of the cantilever beam. The loading was static and was applied by a hydraulic ram operated manually. The load was applied perpendicular to the surface of the beam by a ball and plate arrangement. The plate could swivel or rotate in any direction or rotate and hence maintains continuous contact with the surface of the beam through out the duration of the experiment.

The specimens were tested by applying a force normal to the bottom surface of the beam. Load was applied normal to the surface of the beam till failure. After initial failure, the loading was continued to study the post failure behavior. Loading was done at a higher rate at the beginning of the experiment and the rate was decreased as the predicted load approached. The resulting data points from the transducers were recorded by a Megadec Data Acquisition System. This system recorded data at the rate of one data point per second per transducer for the first test and two data points per second per transducer for the second test. The load was applied and stopped at regular intervals to document the observations and to shoot photographs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The 3-D hybrid solid finite element was used to predict the load capacity of beam-to-column specimens. Four different meshes were examined and the convergence of the results were obtained. Meshing was done by noting the areas which was highly stressed. The number of elements was increased in these areas and also other areas progressively. A total of 3500 elements were used to model both specimens.

The 3-D model was subjected to various loads in order to predict the failure load. The failure load for the first specimen was 600 lb. The normal stress (SYY) contours for the beam-to-column connection under a 600 lb applied load is shown in Figure 2. At this load, maximum shear stress, SXY, and principle stress, S1, did not exceed the strength of the material. But, since the transverse tensile strength of the material is 7 ksi and is less than the maximum SYY (15ksi), therefore, the failure occurs at this load. The maximum normal stress occurs in the junction of the L-shaped angle attached to the web of the beam. Therefore, the joint is most likely to fail in the region of the L-shaped junction of the angle due to stresses higher than the transverse tensile strength of the material.

After analyzing the results obtained from the testing of the first specimen, the angles were added to strengthen the connection (see Fig. 3). The lower angle failed in the first specimen due to delamination while all the other angles remained intact, therefore, reinforcement was provided to this angle only. The contour plot of the normal stress SYY for the second specimen is shown in Figure 4. From this Figure, it is observed that the maximum value of the stress SYY is approximately 16ksi which exceeds the maximum tensile strength in the transverse direction. The maximum normal stress occurs at the junction of the L-shaped reinforcing angle attached to the inside of the beam flange to the column flange and the junction of the lower angle and the adhesive layer. Therefore, the joint is expected to fail in these regions due to stresses higher than the transverse tensile strength of the material at a load of 1100 lbs. It can be seen from the Figures that the stress concentration shifted towards the lower angle and the reinforcing plates when compared to specimen #1.

For the first test the predicted load and displacement were 600 lbs and 0.287 in., respectively, whereas the maximum load and displacement attained experimentally was 630 lbs and the displacement was 0.297 in. The error between the predicted and the test loads was 5% approximately. The failure load from finite element analysis for the second specimen was 1100 lbs, but the highest load attained during the testing was 1169 lbs. The error calculated is nearly 6.3%

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The primary objective of this work was to investigate the behavior of adhesive joints for FRP pultruded beam-to-column connections under static loads. The beam and column were joined with angles bonded by an epoxy structural adhesive. Two specimens were fabricated, the second specimen was built after the first test was concluded to improve upon the first specimen design. Numerical study was done by finite element modeling of the specimens. This study included the modeling of the adhesive joint specimens to obtain the static response of the specimens and the failure loads. Efforts were also made to improve the design of the joint to increase the failure load limit of the second specimen.

By comparing the numerical and experimental results the following conclusions were obtained from this study:

1. The behavior of adhesive joints for composite materials can be accurately predicted by finite element modeling. Special attention should be given to the value of the element aspect ratio. If this value is too high for an element significant error may occur.
2. Epoxy structural adhesives can be used to provide adhesive connections for composite materials in controlled conditions. Hence, the use of these materials in realistic applications might be limited at present.
3. Adhesive joints can be used to connect FRP pultruded sections. However, the details were not able to develop the full strength of the beam.

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REFERENCES

1. Allen, K.W., "A Review of Contemporary Views of Theories of Adhesion," *J. Adhesion*, Vol. 21, 1987, pp. 261-277.
2. Sawa, T., Nakano, Y. et al, "Stress Analysis of T-type Butt Adhesive Joint Subjected to External Bending Moments," *J. Adhesion*, Vol. 24, 1987, pp. 1-15.
3. Yamaguchi, Y., Amano, S. and Sato, S., "Stress Distribution and Strength of T-type Adhesive Joint with Reinforcement for Bending Moments," *J. Adhesion*, Vol. 21, 1987, pp. 195-209.
4. Chen, N.N.S., Niem, P.I.F. and Lee, R.C., "Fatigue Behavior of Adhesive Bonded Joints," *J. Adhesion*, Vol. 21, 1987, pp. 115-128.
5. Mosallam, A.S. and Bank, L.C., "Short-Term Behavior of Pultruded Fiber-Reinforced Plastic Frames," *ASCE J. Structural Engineering*, Vol. 118, No. 7, 1992, pp. 1937-1954.
6. Abd-El-Naby, S.F.M. and Holloway, L., "The Experimental Behavior of Bolted Joints in Pultruded Glass/Polyester Material. Part 1: Single-Bolt Joints," *Composites*, Vol. 24, No. 7, 1993, pp. 531-538.
7. Abd-El-Naby, S.F.M. and Holloway, L., "The Experimental Behavior of Bolted Joints in Pultruded Glass/Polyester Material. Part 2: Two-Bolt Joints," *Composites*, Vol. 24, No. 7, 1993, pp. 539-546.
8. Martin, D.M., "Tests on Transverse Intermediate Web Stiffeners," *Structural Engineer*, Vol. 70, No. 15, August 1992, pp. 261-266.
9. Davies, P., Cantwell, W.J. Jar, P.Y., Bourbon, P.E., Zysman, V. and Kausch, H.H., "Joining and Repair of Carbon Fiber-Reinforced Thermoplastic," *Composites*, Vol. 22, No. 6, November 1991, pp. 425-431.
10. Shi, Y.P. and Cheng, S., "Analysis of Adhesive-Bonded Cylindrical Lap Joints Subjected to Axial Load", *ASCE J. Engineering Mechanics*, Vol. 119, No. 3, March 1993, pp. 584-602.
11. Fusor 320/322 Data Sheet, Lord's Corporation, PA, USA.
12. Design Guide, Creative Pultrusions Inc., Pleasantville Industrial Park, P. O. Box 6, Alum Bank, PA 15521.
13. NISA II, User's Manual, Version 90.0, 1990, EMRC, P. O. Box 696, Troy, MI 48099.
14. Load and Resistance Factor Design, Manual of Steel Construction, AISC, First Edition.

Table 1. Material Properties of FRP Pultruded Components.

PROPERTIES OF BEAM AND ANGLES	Longitudinal	Transverse
Tensile Strength	30 ksi	7 ksi
Tensile Modulus	2500 ksi	----
Shear Strength	5.5 ksi	5.5 ksi
Compressive Strength	30 ksi	15 ksi
Compressive Modulus	2500 ksi	----
PROPERTIES OF COLUMN		
Tensile Strength	37.5 ksi	10 ksi
Tensile Modulus	3000 ksi	----
Shear Strength	7 ksi	6 ksi
Compressive Strength	37.5 ksi	20 ksi
Compressive Modulus	2500 ksi	----

Table 2. Geometric Dimensions of the FRP Pultruded Components.

	Beam	Column
Flange Width	5.0"	6.0"
Flange Thickness	0.37"	0.51"
Web Height	9.20"	10.95"
Web Thickness	0.37"	0.51"
Angle Dimensions	Angles	Reinforcing Angles
L-sides	4.0"	2.0"
Thickness	0.26"	0.26"

- 1 - Hydraulic Ram
- 2,3,4 - Clamping Plates
- 5 - Washer Plate
- 6 - Nut
- 7 - Dywidag Bars
- 8 - Load Cell
- 9,11 - Steel Plates
- 10 - Steel Ball

Figure 1a. Side view of the overall test set-up.

Figure 1b. Section A-A in Figure 2a for specimen #1.

STRESS CONTOURS
 SY Y - STRESSES (psi)
 VIEW : -6.36E+03
 RANGE : 1.55E+04

Band * 1.0E21

Max	155.2
8	60.00
7	42.86
6	25.71
5	8.571
4	-8.571
3	-25.71
2	-42.86
1	-60.00
Min	-155.5

Figure 2. SY Y normal stress contours for specimen #1 using the 3-D hybrid element model.

Figure 3. Section A-A in Figure 1a for specimen #2.

Figure 4. SY Y normal stress contours for specimen #2 using the 3-D hybrid element model.